

EMPOWERING INDIGENOUS PEOPLE (IP'S) COMMUNITIES IN ALBAY, PHILIPPINES USING PURPLE SWEET POTATO PLUS FOOD PRODUCTS

Eden M. Llamera, Ed.D., Engr. Sienna B. Llamera

Technology and Entrepreneurship Department, Bicol University Polangui, Polangui, Albay Philippines

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ABSTRACT

Purple sweet potato is foreseen as one of the root crops that provide colorful appearance in the family meal. The impact of this study illustrates a chain of technology transfer to Indigenous People who were noted of creativity and industry. This study "Empowering Indigenous People Communities in Albay Philippines Using Purple Sweet Potato Plus Food Products," was focused on developing and standardizing recipes using purple sweet potato (*Ipomoea batatas lam.*) variety. The recipes were a combination with other root crops giving higher value enhancing IP's life skills future entrepreneurial activity. The study on physico-chemical characteristics revealed purple sweet potato flour is nutritious having 72.06% MC, 3.34 %ww Ash, 86.265 Carbohydrates, 4.65% Protein and fat 1.015%ww. The raw purple sweet potato has Deep Lilac //Violet, RGB: (66, 63, 104), #8E61BA, HSV: (244°, 39%, 41%), flour with Bouquet //Faded Violet: Pink, after 3 months of storage the color was Fine, pinkish brown powder with L*57.7, a* 10.3, b* 12.1 and h 46.7 using RM 200QC imaging. The 9-point Hedonic scale was used in evaluating the organoleptic and kinesthetic sensory characteristics of each product. Weighted mean aided the interpretation determining the best proportion for each kind. Rank Preference and Kramer's Rank-sum Test result indicated *Purple Sweet Potato Plus Buchipan* as the most preferred product. The IP's enhanced processing skills development got 4.4 weighted mean described as 'Strongly Agree.' A Learning Materials was an output of the study used as a reference in developing processing skills of Indigenous Peoples' in Albay for economic sustainability and resiliency.

Keywords: *plus food products, color retention, standardized, organoleptic and kinesthetic*

INTRODUCTION

According to RA 8371 s. of 1997 Chapter VI, Section 36 on Sustainable Agro Technical Development (1997), the state shall recognize the right of ICCs/IPs to a sustainable agro-technological development and shall formulate and implement programs of action for each effective implementation. The state shall likewise promote bio-genetic and resource management systems among the ICCs/IPs and shall encourage cooperation among government agencies to ensure the successful sustainable development of ICCs/IPs. The university mandate is to conduct researches, provide specialized instruction for social transformation and development. This rationalizes the use of sweet potato and other native crops as an opportunity to explore and provide standardized recipes to help enhance the processing capabilities of “Indigenous People” in Albay. Developing processing skills and integrating the good and cleaner production can provide a support system in producing food products for entrepreneurial commodity. New processing techniques can be used as basis for starting a homebased small business enterprise that can augment family income for “*Indigenous People*” community.

Studying purple sweet potato paved the idea of processing this root crop into flour and determine the color retention and nutrient in it. Processing sweet potatoes present an excellent opportunity for food waste reduction. This is true because most parts of the plant are edible, including leaves, peel, roots, and vines. Regional processors have reported that between 30 and 50% of production typically gets thrown away during processing, but using some creativity, this can be avoidable (DA, 2012). Purple sweet potato is a good source of energy that can supply material that help the body do the activities. Standardizing a recipe for the purple sweet potato can build a reference providing step by step procedures that can be followed to make a wholesome food product.

According to Types of Sweet Potatoes-Complete List and Guide (2022), Sweet potato is classified as a dicotyledonous plant or a vine species, sweet potatoes belong to the morning glory family Convolvulaceae with scientific name of *Ipomoea batatas lam.* Many recipes were developed from its roots, which are tube-like, starchy, sweet, having vibrant-colored root vegetable consumed and loved. Sweet potato is rich in fiber, vitamins, and minerals, having anti-oxidant properties. This type of vegetable root crop help in supporting healthy vision due to its vitamin A content, and Vitamin C boosting the immune system, and even fight off cancer-causing toxins (Turong, 2018). One of the impressive about colorful sweet potato is that they offer fantastic benefits like anthocyanins and rich in anti-oxidants.

Mohanraj and Sivansankar (2014), studied on giving a bird's-eye view of the nutritional value, health benefits, phytochemical composition, and medicinal properties of sweet potato. Specifically, this review outlines the biological activities of some of the sweet potato compounds that have been isolated, the pharmacological action of the sweet

potato extract, clinical studies, and plausible medicinal applications of sweet potato and demonstrates the potential of sweet potato as a medicinal food. The study gave a vision of studying the purple sweet potato physico-chemical characteristics to have a notably formation of nutritive content of the local harvest of purple sweet potato.

One of the studies conducted was the development of a process for producing sweet potato chips. "Sweet potato tubers sliced to 0.5 by 0.5 cm size were dehydrated at 70 degrees C for various times (0, 90, 105, 120, 135, 150, 165 minutes Baldwin, (2023). The determination of the moisture content of the dehydrated chips and sensory evaluation of the dehydrated and fried chips were carried out to establish optimum dehydration time and moisture which corresponded to optimum quality the same way as the chip's recipe in the present study which differ in using the purple sweet potato variety, the time and style variates in different ways. The significance of this study with the present study showing the same intent but of different procedures and findings. Moreover, the present study, have developed different recipes and made a compilation of each into a learning material purposively providing a reference for household consumption or for entrepreneurial activity.

Pulverizing and retaining the purple color of sweet potato is a challenge that this research has to unfold. This variety is known for its sensitivity to processing. It has an enzyme that when not exposed to sun or dried after chopping, it easily gets spoiled. The cause for the demand of sweet potato starch in the Philippines is due to the extraction rate and the finished product is of good quality. The study reveals the drying time and the rasping machine plays a key role, and the most common starch grating machine on the market today is the RU series of super rasping machine (Olantunde et.al., 2016). The sun drying are method appropriated to IP's conventional technology for milling while food processing steps are simple and can be followed. The purple color in sweet potato is retained even after series of sun drying and rigorous pulverizing processes.

In the study of De Los Santos, Maat and Ventura (2017), imparted the tuberous root of orange sweet potato variety into ketchup. The Raw orange sweet potato (OSP) and the developed ketchup were subjected to proximate, total dietary fiber, Vitamin A analysis, physicochemical and microbiological analysis. The proximate analysis of the ketchup showed that OSP ketchup is a poor source of protein (0.53g/100g) and fat (none-detected). However, the ash content increased (2.1g/100g) and there is a decrease of carbohydrate content (18.77g/100g) due to the process of boiling. The utilization of orange sweet potato motivated the researcher to use the purple sweet potato by creating six (6) different food products. The acceptability of the purple sweet potato plus food products was sought. The color retention and physico-chemical attributes described that local purple variety is a potential commodity producing quality colorful food products for entrepreneurial commodity.

According to Lirag (2019), a study on sweet potato has found its niche in the global market and is now outpacing other primary staple foods not only because of its desirability for human consumption but as an immediate source of income. The study examined the factors affecting the profitability of sweet potato production in Camarines Sur, Philippines.

The researcher used purposive sampling technique to select the 108 farmer-respondents. A structured questionnaire was used and focused group discussion were the main tools for gathering data. Cost and return analysis and return on investment were used to determine the profitability of sweet potato production. This study cited were considered related to the present study in determining the marketability of the different purple sweet potato plus food products.

This study used the purple variety of sweet potato giving full potential for possible entrepreneurial food products. The importance of purple color was considered to make a colorful food without using artificial coloring. Its natural purple color is known for rich in antioxidants, energy, and vitamin content. This study has an aspiration of increasing awareness on the beauty and nutritional benefits from sweet purple potato. Standardized food products will be taught to indigenous communities identified native local folks' communities. The importance of helping the indigenous people is a priority of this research. Indeed, enhancing the processing capability of IP's using purple sweet potato is a valued achievement of this study.

Research Questions

The general objectives of the study were focused on Empowering Indigenous People Communities in Albay Philippines Using Sweet Potato Plus Food Products. The study was focused on the development and standardization of purple sweet potato plus food products enhancing the processing capability of the Indigenous People in Albay teaching life-skills for sustainable economic development. Specifically, it sought the following: (1) determine the physico-chemical characteristics of the colored sweet potato as to: weight and dimension, %usable parts, %moisture content, % flour recovery, color retention, yeast & mold count and proximate analysis of the flour; (2) develop and standardize the correct proportions of ingredients and procedures of the colored Sweet Potato Plus Food Products; (3) Test the acceptability of the Sweet Potato Plus Food Product in terms of organoleptic and kinesthetic characteristics; (4) Determine the most preferred product and its fat content; (5) Identify the potential marketability of the colored sweet potato plus food products; (6) Create a Learning Materials on processing of sweet potato plus food product for enhance processing capability of the indigenous people in Albay, Philippines.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive research is a process of describing the characteristics of the population or phenomenon studied. It focuses on the “what” and “why” of the research subject (McCombes, 2023). It was understood that descriptive research “describes” the subject without covering “why” it happens. This methodology was used to described the phenomena on the acceptability of the food products by the 20 IP respondents of the study. Trials were made in standardizing the different recipes of the purple sweet potato. These recipes were compiled in a learning material a reference used in the enhancing of processing capability of the indigenous people using sweet potato plus food products.

Figure 1. The Paradigm of Methodology of the Study

The product development and standardization of the recipes were lay on formulating a new product using trial method. Correct proportions of ingredients were tried until the acceptable color, aroma, taste and texture were achieved. It is very important to note that the market potential of sweet potato products are constantly increasing with 5.9% and 6.7% respectively (DA Guide, 2020). The taste the presentations of foods are important aspect to consider the salability of these produce. The technique of processing procedures considers the entire life journey of a product that an indigenous people can easily understood to follow. The acceptability of the finished food products used 9-point Hedonic scale in evaluating the organoleptic characteristics as to aroma, color, and taste,

while kinesthetic characteristics evaluate the mouthfeel and texture. The weighted mean was used in the interpretation on the “level of acceptability” of the food products. The Rank Preference Test was used in selecting the most preferred product. The Kramer’s Rank-sum Test aid in determining the “level of significance difference” among the products. At the end, the standardized accepted recipes were compiled in a Learning Material Modeling the Processing of Purple Sweet Potato Plus Food Products for Enhancing the Processing Capabilities of the IP’s was an output of the study.

RESULTS

The NSIC-SP 25 purple sweet potato variety was used in standardization of the food products. The purple variety is locally known as “inubi” (purple) . This is a special type of sweet potato having a distinct characteristic compared to other varieties. Rich purple color on food provides phytochemicals known as anthocyanins. According to studies, the best source of anthocyanins component is purple and blue color which is present in purple sweet potato. The “antioxidant effects have been linked to lower risk of myocardial infarction in young and middle-aged women.” These nutritional qualities are unnoticed, thus giving importance to the great nutrition benefits. The purpose of processing purple sweet potato into flour is to give a longer shelf-life and economic value of ready to use flour. This resonates in giving value on propagating and producing the sweet potato purple variety.

3.1. The Physico-Chemical Characteristics of Purple Sweet Potato

3.1.1 Weight and Dimension

The study used 10 samples of different sizes to get the average weight and dimension of purple sweet potato. An electronic vernier caliper was used to get the dimensions of the samples of raw potato. Table 1 showed different weight and dimension with an average, 12.5 centimeters, 18.05 centimeters circumference and length with 176 centimeters respectively. It is common to purple sweet potato to have medium size, not too big or small neither.

3.1.2. Percent (%) Usable Parts

The percent usable parts reveal data on how many parts of the purple sweet potato are removed and how many are used in producing flour from the samples. The 2,000 grams or 2 kilos of purple sweet potato used as sample for producing flour. From the sample, the waste part has 60.5 grams, minimal waste was observed because the peel was not removed and only trimmings are discarded from the sweet potato rhizomes. It can be noted that there were 96.95% (percent) usable parts or 1,934.5 grams of the purple sweet potato were used for flour production.

3.1.3. Percent (%) Moisture Content

For easy drying, the chipped purple sweet potato was thinly chopped using the thickness of 0.02 mm. The chips were dried under the heat of the sun for 8 days. The drying started at 8:00 o'clock in the morning until 4:00 o'clock in the afternoon to get the peak heat from the sunlight. It consumed 8 consecutive days or 64 hours to fully dry the raw chips.

Table 1. The % Moisture Content of the Dried Chips Purple Sweet Potato Using Sundried Method

Day	Weight (g)	% MC
0	1,935.5	-
1	1,740.6	10.06
2	1,533	20.79
3	1,222,87	36.81
4	998.5	48. 41
5	775.65	59.92
6	624.1	68
7	601.7	69
8	540.6	72.06

The final moisture content was very important in milling processes of the raw chips. The chips should have the hard crisp chips texture to get the fineness of a flour. The removed moisture of purple sweet potato was recorded with 72.06% removed moisture after 8 days from continued sun drying. The retained moisture content during the pulverizing of the purple sweet potato chips was 27. 94% which was higher than normal standard storage of wheat with 11% moisture.

3.1.4. Percent (%) Flour Recovery

The Purple Sweet Potato was milled using the rice milling technology. After milling there was 445.65 grams or 82.43% flour recovery.

Weight of the recovered flour after milling	-	445.65
Divide by the original weight of the sample	-	/540.6
Quotient obtained	-	.8243
Multiplied by 100	-	x100
% Flour recovery	-	82.43%

3.1.5. Color Retention of Purple Sweet Potato Flour

The raw purple sweet potato has a color of sweet purple with a little of white strands on its whole crop grain. This variety is recognized upon looking at the vine of rhizomes. The presence of deep violet color can be seen in stem of the leaf of purple sweet potato. For

scientific data, a colorimeter is used to determine what type of purple color found in this crop.

Using a Computer Information Engineering (CEI) standard illuminant D65 and standard observer (2°), the raw purple sweet potato has a deep lilac color in in a colorimeter with a following:

Raw Chips

Flour

Plate 1. The Raw and the Processed Flour of Purple Sweet Potato

The color family of the purple sweet potato is “Deep Lilac” belonging to Violet #8E61BA, with Red 66, Green 63, and Blue 104 values, Hue Saturation Values of 244°, 39%, 41% of the red, green and blue respectively, Registry Abstraction Layer (RAL) Code of 4011 as Pearl Violet or Violet.

The color of the powdered purple sweet potato was a real light purple or having a lavender hue. The texture of the flour when rubbed between fingers was a little grainy or rough. The aroma was nice and sweet. The color was naturally nude pale violet, Bouquet “Faded Violet: Pink” is likely the true color as revealed in the results. The cooked flour was been observed having a very dark color when processed purple sweet potato plus into food products. All of the three products from steamed, fried chips and even processed flour added with other ingredients, have noted with dark color of deep violet. The cooked produced becomes almost black color in the human naked eye showed a registry abstraction layer (RAL) has 4007/Purple violet or fall into #4F293A described as Dark Violet-Pink.

Table 2. Report of Analysis on the Color Retention of the Purple Sweet Potato Flour after 3 months of storage

Item No.	Sample & Lab Code	Sample Description	Parameter	Method Used	Result
			L*	TM-Ch-070 with reference to	57.7
	Purple Sweet Potato Flour	Fine pinkish brown powder	a*	RM200QC Imaging Spectrometer	10.3
1	(CHE-0565)	in plastic	b*		12.1
		1x ~ 100g	C*		15.9
			h	(CIEL*a*b* and CIE L*C*h Color Space)	48.7

3.1.6. The Yeast and Mold Count of the Purple Sweet Potato flour

Longer storage of a flour depends on the slowing of microbial growth of the yeast and molds in the purple sweet potato flour. The growth of yeast and mold in the flour can cause deterioration and may lead to early spoilage of a product. Occurrence of abnormal color, flavor and odor was an indicator that the flour is already infested by bacteria or yeast and molds that deter taste and palatability. A flour may seem to be as mold free but when subjected into microbial test it is already contaminated with bacteria after 3 months of storage. To assure its edibility the purple Sweet Potato flour was tested at DOST Region V for a laboratory examination on yeast and mold count.

The yeast and mold was already present in three months of storage having 3.9×10^4 coliforming unit. This indicates that the flour was already infested with bacteria making it unfit for human consumption. The presence of colony forming units in the flour was an indicator that it is no longer clean and safe. This is true to the stored purple sweet potato flour characterized by slight off odor, aflatoxins taste, caking texture and growth of weevils in the flour. According to standards, the allowable amount for human ingestions of yeast and mold will only have $\leq 10,000$ CFU/g to avoid fatalities and complications. Therefore, the shelf-life of the purple sweet potato flour expires in 3 months of storage .

3.1.7. Proximate Analysis of Purple Sweet Potato Flour

The proximate analysis is a scientific method used to determine the approximate amounts of substances within purple sweet potato flour. The percentage of components within the food material in purple sweet potato flour can contribute to its nutritive value and flexibility when combined to other ingredients to make a delectable food product. The test was done to emphasize important nutrient that are present in the locally processed flour. The 250g of Purple Sweet Potato Flour contains the following: Moisture 5.14 %ww; Ash, 3.34 %ww; Protein 4.65 (Block Digestion -Kjeildahl); Fat, 1.01 %ww; Carbohydrate,

86.28 %ww. The essential source of anti-oxidant revealed the following: Fiber: 3.3 grams, Manganese: 6% of the Daily Value (DV), Copper: 21% of the DV, Iron: 2% of the DV, Potassium: 8% of the DV, Vitamin B6: 18% of the DV, Vitamin C:14% of the DV.

It can be noted that the purple sweet potatoes are a good source of beta-carotene. It is even richer source of anthocyanin pigments, characterized by its purple color. The antioxidants can help reduce inflammation and boost immune system. Purple sweet potatoes have about three times richer in anthocyanin content as signified by its deep purple color. The deeper purple color the richer the vitamin content it has.

3.2. The Standardized Recipes of Purple Sweet Potato Plus Food Products

Standardization of recipes pave an important set of instructions for making a food dish from various ingredients. The recipe provides the amounts and proportions of ingredients and methods of procedures that will consistently produce a high-quality food product. There are six Purple Sweet Potato Plus Food Products prepared by the study.

The recipes used two material processes, used the raw rhizomes for standardizing the following recipes: There were 4 products such as Flavored Purple Sweet Potato Chips, Purple Sweet Potato Plus Candy, Sweet Purple Banban and Nutri Purple Sweet Potato Jam uses raw purple variety, all others used the flour. The standardized recipes are having simple procedures, easy to prepare and follow.

3.2.1 Flavored Purple Sweet Potato Chips

Ingredients: 1 kilo Purple Sweet Potato, ½ Teaspoon salt, 2 Kilos Oil (for Frying) and 1 Pack Cheese of Barbeque Flavor.

Procedure:

Wash thoroughly camote rhizomes. Drain until dry. Cut into chips about 0.2 cm thick or as desired (using chipper). Drizzle with salt leave for 1 minute. Heat oil until hot. Deep fry the purple sweet potato raw chips. Cook by stirring to avoid burning of chips. When chippy texture is obtained, take it out off from the oil and immediately drain off the oil. Let it cool Put inside a plastic bag and pour in the cheese or barbeque flavor and shake a little to adhere the flavor onto the chips. Pack into individual packs. Label.

3.2.2. Purple Sweet Potato Plus Candy

Ingredients:1 cup cooked and mashed purple sweet potato, 2/3 cup white sugar, 1 tablespoon butter, ½ cup powdered milk, ½ cup chopped Pilinuts.

Procedure; Wash the raw sweet potato and boil to cook. Removed the peel and mashed until obtained fine texture. Mix all ingredients. Put all mixed ingredients in a carajay. Cook mixture in a very low fire. Continue stirring to prevent from sticking

into the pan. Continue stirring until the mixture becomes soft hard but pliable. Remove from fire when mixture forms a ball while being stirred. Flatten the mixture in a prepared greased pan while hot. Divide the mixture into desired sizes. Let it cool. Wrap into a colored cellophane or desired wrapper. Pack and label.

3.2.3. Nutri-Purple Sweet Potato Plus Jam

Ingredients: 3 cups Raw Purple Sweet Potato, 1 cup white Taro, 2 cups sugar, 2 cans evaporated milk (big can), 2 Teaspoon vanilla..

Procedure: Peel both purple sweet potato and taro. Wash thoroughly to remove soil from the rhizomes. Grate the rhizomes into fine coarse texture. Set aside. Pour into carajay the following: Milk, sugar and mix together. Dissolve sugar thoroughly and add the taro and sweet purple potato. Cook in a low fire until thick like a jam. Cook until spreadable texture is obtained. Cool and pack in a sterilized jar. Pasteurized the product for about 30 minutes. Remove from water and pat dry. Put label. Seal.

3.2.4. Empanaditas Con Inube

Ingredients for the dough (crust): 3 cups All Purpose Flour, 1 1/2 bar butter, 1 tablespoon sugar, pinch of salt 10 tablespoon of cold water.

Procedure for the crust: Sift flour, sugar in a bowl. Add butter. Mix the butter, sugar and flour using a fork in cutting motion. Continue cutting butter into flour until pea size is obtained. Divide the mixture into small balls. Flatten the balls and put onto Empanaditas molder or cutter. Fill in with nutri-purple sweet potato jam. Close the edges using molder. Cut off excess mixture. See to it that the Empanaditas is fully close by putting a pressure onto the edge of dough. Heat oil. Deep fry until golden brown texture on the crust is achieve. Drain let it cool. Pack and label. Filling: Nutri-Purple Sweet Potato Plus Jam

3.2.5. The Food products from Purple Sweet Potato Flour

There were only two standardized food products developed using the purple sweet potato flour. These products use simple procedures and requires simple technology so that the indigenous people could follow the step-by-step procedures in preparing the food products.

3.2.6. Purple Sweet Potato Plus Buchipan

Ingredients: 1 ½ cup hot water, 2/3 cup white sugar, 3 cups sticky rice flour, ½ cup Purple Sweet Potato flour. Sesame seeds (for coating), Oil for frying.

Procedures: Combine hot water and sugar. Mix until it thoroughly dissolved. Pour in little by little the sticky rice and purple sweet potato flour. Mix thoroughly for 2-3 minutes until well combined. Close mixture with cloth. Rest mixture for 15 minutes.

After 15 minutes, form mixture into rod and cut into desired weight. Form into a ball. Flatten the balls using the heel of the palm. Put in the filling (Nutri-Purple Sweet Potato Plus Jam). Seal and set aside until all are form into round ball. Roll onto sesame seeds, until well coated. Heat oil and deep fry. When Buchipan is already light brown, when balls are already floating on top of oil it is an indication that the Buchipan is cook. Get it from oil and drain. Let it cool. Pack and label.

3.2.7. Sweet Purple Banban

Ingredients: 2 cups Purple Sweet Potato Flour, 1 cup sticky rice flour, 1 cup shredded buko, 1 ½ cup sugar, 2 tablespoon vanilla, 2 cups evaporated milk (big can), Banana leaves (for wrapping of mixture)

Procedures: In a bowl mix purple sweet potato flour and sticky rice, sugar. Pour in milk and vanilla. Mix well until blended. Add Buko and blend well. Pour mixture in a banana leaf and close by folding both ends very well. Arrange all Banban into a kettle and steam for 30 minutes or until cook. Cool and serve with brown rice coffee.

3.3. The Acceptability Purple Sweet Potato Plus Products using Organoleptic and Kinesthetic Characteristics

There were six (6) different purple sweet potato plus food product accepted by the respondents emphasizing the qualitative descriptive analysis and interpretations in the attributed likelihood of the product:

The flavored purple sweet potato chips are having a deep dark purple color. The chip's cracking texture was crispy noted with a good balance of taste of sweet potato and flavorings. The chips are a bit comparable having a texture like but a little harder than of the commercialized potato chips in the market. An observation showing smear was noted and the oil inside was visible but it doesn't affect the texture of the product. Indeed, the acceptability in taste showed the general weighted mean of 7.26 having a qualitative descriptive interpretation of 'Like Moderately.'

The purple sweet potato plus candy was made up of steamed purple sweet potato and Pilinuts added with other ingredients. The candy was cut into a bar and packed. The level of acceptability of the candy showed on aroma with weighted mean of 6.4 described as "Like Moderately." The aroma of gentle sweet mediated the receptors of taste buds having just enough sweet obtaining a weighed mean of 7.34 described as "Like Moderately" respectively.

The nutri-purple sweet potato plus jam obtained the weighted mean of 7.89 for color attributes with a qualitative description of "Likely Very Much." The combinations of ingredients showed strong likelihood of the product. The prominence of the sweet potato taste was noted with highest weighted mean of 8.36 interpreted as "Like Very Much."

The Empanaditas con Inube is delicious product from purple sweet potato. Hence, the soft crispy crust was a remarkable characteristic of Empanaditas. Emphasizing taste of sweetness and saltiness blend together producing a sumptuous food product. The taste and texture almost same to each other obtaining a weighted mean of 8.1 for taste and 8.0 for texture have a qualitative description of “Like Very Much” respectively.

Figure 2. The Acceptability of the Purple Sweet Potato Plus Food Products in Terms of Kinesthetic and Organoleptic Characteristics

The Purple Sweet Potato Plus Buchipan showed a remarkable likelihood among the flour by-products. It has a general weighted mean of 7.91 having a qualitative descriptive

interpretation of “Like Very Much.” The color and taste of the Buchanan was noted as the most accepted product with a weighted mean of 8.02 and 8.34, respectively. Among all the standardized product sweet purple Banban was known for native delicacy that are commonly prepared for snacks. These products can be prepared using either raw or flour. This Banban used the sweet potato flour together with other ingredients. The Banban uses milk instead of water which makes it more delicious and nutritious food product. It can be noted that the observation of having a good taste was supported by its level of acceptability on taste having a weighted mean of 8.08 with a qualitative descriptive interpretation of “Like Very Much.”

3.4. The Most Preferred Product

The rank preference test is commonly used in selecting the best products using the level of ranks from the value given or assigned as to which is the best product or the worst product as perceived by the respondents. Table 3 showed the results on best product preferences. This is the most appropriate statistical tool on determining food product preferences. The following steps were done to arrive at correct analysis for most preferred product.

Among the 20 respondents (n=20) who evaluated 6 different sample samples (R=6) using the 5% level of significance, the corresponding ranks in the Kramer’s Rank-sum test used the 52-88 range to test its level of significance. It showed that the H_0 of the study stated that when sum of the samples falls in the range or within the range given all of the samples will no differ from each other. If the total sum of each type falls below or above the range given, it can be said the product that has a lower or higher value will be declared as the odd or different sample from the other sample. The “Purple Sweet Potato Plus Buchipan” obtained a lower rank sum of 41 describe as the odd sample, is the “Most Preferred Product.’

Table 3. The Ranking for Preference for Standardized Recipes of Purple Sweet Potato Plus Food Products

Panelists	Rank per Sample					
	N-PSPJ	PSPPCan	FPSPCh	Ecl	PSPPB	SPB
1	6	5	2	3	1	4
2	5	1	3	6	2	4
3	2	3	1	4	5	6
4	1	4	5	6	2	3
5	2	5	4	3	1	6
6	1	5	6	3	2	4
1	2	5	6	3	2	4
8	2	5	6	3	1	4
9	3	5	6	4	2	1
10	6	5	4	3	1	2
11	2	5	6	3	1	4
12	6	1	3	2	4	5

13	1	5	4	2	3	6
14	6	3	4	2	1	5
15	3	6	4	1	2	5
16	6	3	4	2	5	1
17	6	3	4	1	2	5
18	2	6	4	3	1	5
19	2	6	4	3	1	5
20	1	6	5	4	2	3
Total Rank	65	87	85	61	41	82
Rank 1 = Best and Rank 6 = Worst						

The Fat content of the most preferred product.

Fat is needed for the properly absorption of fat-soluble vitamins in human body. It adds flavor to food products with distinct satiety. Human needs fat to help the brain cells function well, besides needing it in maintaining supple knees and glossy hair. Result of analysis provides for every 25g of Nutri-Purple Sweet Potato Plus Buchipan there were 133 calories, 8 g of fat, 0.7 g of protein, 15 g of carbohydrate and 2.3 g sugar.

3.5. Potential Marketability of Purple Sweet Potato Plus Food Products

There were 50 consumers responders were asked if they would buy Purple Sweet Potato Plus Food Products and these were their responses. It can be noted that Purple Sweet Potato Plus Buchipan (PSPPB) have 14 or 28% willingness of buying the product, ranks second is Empanaditas con Inube with indicated 10 or 20% willingness to buy. Meanwhile the Nutri-Purple Sweet Potato Jam got 8 or 16%, Purple Sweet Potato Candy got 7 or 14% while Sweet Purple Banban got 6 or 12% and Flavored Purple Sweet Potato Chips got 5 or 10% willingness to buy respectively.

The illustration on marketability goes to show that “Purple Sweet Potato Plus Buchipan” was the most preferred product that customers would like to buy followed by Empanaditas con “Inube (Purple).: The products are marketable and could be used as the homebased products for the *IP* community.

3.6 The Learning Materials on Processing Purple Sweet Potato Plus Food Products: Enhancing the Processing Capability of the Indigenous People in Selected Municipality in Albay, Philippines

3.6.1 Prologue

The learning materials on processing purple sweet potato into food products is a useful material that can be disseminated to households specifically the Indigenous People

community. This learning material will serve as a reference to facilitate the learning of the local folks.

The learning materials contain simple recipes that can be followed by the learners. All food products use raw materials that are available in the local market and in the farm of the community. Processing is simple and can be followed by anyone who got interest in processing local foods. Besides, the featured food product will not alter the culture of the *IP's* but rather will enhance their food processing skills integrating the cleaner good manufacturing standards for food safety.

Food products that are presented in this Learning Materials is modelling a simple but delicious and nutritious food product. This can be used as family business items that can be marketable in the community. The products draw demand because of its sumptuous taste that can fully provide energy when consumed. The products contain no preservatives added, natural color is coming from its natural purple pigment. The products are used as food, snacks and appetizers too. This product is rich in "*Flavonoids Vitamins*" an anti-oxidant with high nutritive content of carbohydrate and protein. (Note: the Learning Materials were written separately)

3.6.2. Results of the Initializing Training of the Indigenous People using the Learning Materials on Processing Purple Sweet Potato Plus, Food Products

The results on initializing training were taken from 16 respondents during the training conducted in June 27-28, 2022 at BUPC Dormstel participated by selected Indigenous People from Malabnig, Guinobatan; Danao, Polangui; and Joroan, Tiwi, Albay. This was an in-house live-in training. The trainees were given an training for 2 days to see if they could learn and can improve their processing skills using the purple sweet potato plus food products. The evaluation of the training has a 4.7 weighted mean which interpreted as 'Strongly Agree.' This means that the training proceedings were acceptable and believed to enhance the processing capability of the Indigenous People. On the other hand, on the item number 11, in the question "training time allotment was sufficient" got only 4.4 weighted mean which interpreted 'strongly agree.' The training time was sufficient to cover all the important skills to be developed during the training.

3.6.3 Enhanced Processing Capability of the Indigenous People Using Sweet Potato Plus Food Products

The training was intended to form and develop the processing capability of the indigenous people in selected municipality in Albay using purple sweet potato plus food products. A questionnaire was given to the 16 trainees who were actively participated in the initializing training for enhanced processing capability using purple sweet potato plus food products. During the training each were given a learning material to read. A lecture, demonstration and return demonstration were performed carrying out the actual application of food processing. Each of the trainees were given an opportunity to illustrate a capability on

processing the recipes shown in the learning materials for Purple Sweet Potato Plus Food recipes.

3.6.4 Results on Enhanced Processing Skills Capability of the Indigenous People

The data showed that the IP's can identify the ingredients that has been used in preparing the different recipes of the purple sweet potato plus food products showing a weighted mean of 4.8 and has the ability to present food product with a rating of 4.8 which was described as "Strongly Agree" respectively.

DISCUSSION

Physical characteristics of the sweet potato were as follows: the average weight and dimension of the 10 samples was 12.5cm length, circumference 18.05cm, and 176 gram. The Percent usable parts were 96.8% and got at moisture content of 72.06%, flour recovery of 82.43%.

Color retention for raw purple sweet potato is deep lilac violet with a Registry Abstraction Layer (RAL) of 4001 Pearl Violet. The color of the new processed purple sweet potato flour was Bouquet, Faded Violet with Registry Abstraction Layer of 4009 Pastel Violet. After 3 months of storage the color becomes fine pinkish brown. The color of the processed products of steamed potato four have a Registry Abstraction Layer of 4007 as purple violet and fall into #4F described as Dark Violet-Pink.

Yeast and mold count of the stored purple sweet potato was having 39x10⁴ CFU*/g. The results on Proximate analysis for the flour using 250 grams sample, it has a moisture of 5.14%, ash of 3.34%, protein of 4.65% ant fat of 1.01% and carbohydrate content of 86.28%.

Standardized recipes were the following: Flavored Purple Sweet Potato, Purple Sweet Potato Plus Candy, Nutri-Purple Sweet Potato Jam, Empanaditas con Inube, Purple Sweet Potato Buchipan, Sweet Purple Banban.

The acceptability of the Purple Sweet Potato on organoleptic and kinesthetic characteristics reveals the following: Flavored Purple Sweet Potato Chips got a weighted mean of 7.16, Purple Sweet Potato Plus Candy with 7.25 described as "Like Moderately" respectively. The Empanaditas con Inube with 7.72 which have a qualitative description of 'Like Very Much,' meanwhile the highest weighted obtained among the sample products was Nutri-purple Sweet Potato Jam with 7.89 with qualitative descriptive analysis of 'Like Very Much.' Sweet Potato Flour Food Products showed Purple Sweet Potato Buchipan weighted mean of 7.82 described as Like Very Much, Sweet Purple Banban weighted mean of 7.57 interpreted as "Like Very Much." The most preferred product Purple Sweet Potato Plus Buchipan with a Total Rank of 41 as significance different sample among others.

There were 8 grams of fat per 250 grams sample of Purple Sweet Potato Plus Buchipan Food Product.

The potential marketability showed Purple Sweet Potato Plus Buchipan of 28% likeness, Empanaditas con Inube with 20%, Nutri-Purple Sweet Potato Jam have 16%, Purple Sweet Potato Candy 14%, Sweet Purple Banban 12%, Flavored-Purple Sweet Potato Chips got 10%.

Learning Material for Enhancing Processing Capability of Indigenous People in Selected Musicality in Albay was presented. The initializing training evaluation got 4.7 general weighted mean which describes as 'Strongly Agree,' and the enhance processing capability of the indigenous people got 4.4 general weighted mean which was described as "Strongly Agree' respectively.

Conclusions

In summary, physico-chemical characteristics of the purple sweet potato are of notable importance to assume that the local farm products are nutritious and can provide full energy consumptions to human needs. Color of purple sweet potato is retained even after processing and storing of the flour. Recipes on Purple Sweet Potato were standardized and can be a potential food merchandise in the market. Food products can be introduced to children to have new choice of snacks to offer in the school canteens.

The most preferred food product was Purple Sweet Potato Plus Buchipan. Production of these food products can be a potential entrepreneurial engagement of IP's, household, or gender as an additional income for the family. Learning Materials on Processing Purple Sweet Potato Plus Food Product was a tool in enhancing the processing capability of the indigenous People in Albay, Philippines. These learning materials can be a potential reference to teach simple recipes that are easy to follow and have it sold in the customers. Use of the Training Plan and Learning materials as the output of the study impliedly enhanced the processing capability of the indigenous people using sweet potato plus food products, can be continuously implemented in the extension program of the college.

Recommendations

The educational resources that have been produced are extremely valuable for university extension activities. It is possible to apply for utility model and copyright patent applications for additional recipes. A compilation book that contains standardized recipes and processes is currently being developed. It is highly recommended to actively promote the wide distribution of these educational resources to other educational institutions.

Additionally, it is encouraged to explore research opportunities for other agricultural products.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research complied with the Ethical Standards required by Bicol University Research and Development Management Office upon approval by the University President. Likewise, this research was approved by the Director of National Commission on Indigenous People Office Region V Iriga City, Camarines Sur. Hence, all activities were highly coordinated with the said offices, Indigenous People Chieftains, Municipal Mayors and Barangay Chairman of the respondents of the study. The output of the study were used to train the selected Indigenous People in Albay to improve their processing capability using the local root crops grown in the locality for sustainable economic development.

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